

Research article

Linguistic motives common to Japanese and Romance dialects Two examples with maps

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Abstract: Linguistic data treatment and mapping can vary greatly depending on the choices made by dialectologists. After recalling the fundamental principles of traditional geolinguistics, this article introduces the motivational point of view and the possibilities it presents in terms of mapping dialectal data. Concepts such as *désignant* and *motive* help focus on the ideas, interpretations and worldviews that are so important to lexical creation and change. By using them to classify the dialectal lexicon, we have found great similarities between the data of the *Linguistic Atlas of Japan* (LAJ) and the *Atlas Linguistique Roman* (ALiR). Those similarities transcend cultural differences. The two main examples that we map and analyze are 'praying mantis' and 'tadpole'. Both in Japan and in the Romance world, the former is generally named after its posture that looks like it is praying or after its bladelike limbs, when it is not seen as some kind of a (holy) horse. The latter gets its names from the fact that it is a baby frog, that it has a big head or that its shape is reminiscent of kitchen utensils. Our motivational maps show that such motives are massively shared by Japanese and Romance dialects as they cover a significant part of both areas. This rules out the possibility that they are due to chance. Etymologists already take advantage of this kind of discovery, that opens up new fields of research at the intersection of linguistics and cognitive sciences.*

Keywords: Linguistic motivation; Romance dialects; Japanese dialects; Praying mantis; Tadpole

1. Traditional dialectology and geolinguistics

1.1. A study of forms

The first major geolinguistic projects date back to the turn of the 20th century, with the monumental *Atlas Linguistique de la France* (ALF) in the West and the smaller *Phonetic Dialect Atlas* (PDA) / *Grammatical Dialect Atlas* (GDA) in Japan. Whether dealing with the lexicon, grammatical morphemes or purely phonetic aspects, the

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general principle of this kind of undertaking is to present linguistic forms (i.e. phonetic types, figurative pronunciations, signifiers) on a map.

This form-focused approach, referred to in these pages as “traditional”, proved to be extremely productive. Its general mapping model, continually reproduced to this day, demonstrates the durability of this tried-and-tested method. More than a century later, the fourth and final volume of the *Atlas Linguistique et ethnographique de la Provence* (ALP), follows the exact same pattern as the ALF, with lexical maps showing the raw dialectal phonetic form of all the localities surveyed for a given meaning (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1 ALF (1902-1910) (left) et ALP IV (2016) (right): an established model

1.2. A certain amount of cartographic diversity

This durability does not, however, rule out any freedom in the presentation of data. Alongside the raw data atlases characteristic of the old French tradition, we find atlases of interpreted data, in which data deemed to be of a similar nature are grouped together and represented by signs, colors, or a combination of the two. The Japanese tradition provides excellent examples of this. The geolinguist may also be tempted to represent homogeneous areas by drawing isoglosses (Fig. 2) or producing colored area maps.

Fig. 2 The isoglosses in the *Atlas Linguistique et ethnographique du Massif Central* (ALMC)

1.3. Results of all kinds

There have been countless advances in geolinguistics, from elucidating the history and spread of individual items (from this point of view, some analyses have become famous, such as Gilliéron’s study of rooster names in Gascony), to identifying the external factors – particularly territorial ones (Fig. 3) – that structure linguistic diffusion in a particular dialect area, or to developing terminology and proposing theoretical models of word circulation.

Fig. 3 Drainage basins of France and 4 examples of lexical distribution (Brun-Trigaud & Le Berre & Le Dù, 2005:134)

1.4. The arbitrariness of the sign as axiom

The basic theoretical foundation of this long tradition can be found in Saussure's arbitrary sign (2005 [1916]: 100–103). From arbitrariness flows the principle of the continuity of areas, as described by Dauzat (1922: 42):

An area that today appears dislocated and fragmented once formed a continuous whole. [...] Since ideas have only factual relationships with expressions, the identity of a root or a form in two different languages to designate the same thing or the same function cannot be the effect of chance, but proves the kinship of the two types, i.e. their prior common existence.

This principle enables Dauzat to assert, for example, that the dialectal distributions of *pott-* 'lips' and its derivative *poton* 'kiss', now scattered across southwestern France, Savoy and the Vosges (Fig. 4), are the remnants of an ancient homogeneous area. These lexical types necessarily predate the Roman conquest, but they declined with the introduction of Latin.

Fig. 4 The distribution of *pott-* 'lips' and *poton* 'kiss' according to the ALF

2. A complementary perspective: motivation

2.1. From arbitrariness to motivation

Once the advantages of the traditional approach were well known, and the methodological apparatus was firmly established within the community of dialectologists, recent decades have seen the development of a new point of view, which is intended to complement standard practices. With this approach, the researcher's gaze can shift from the form to the idea, or representation of the world that underlies that form. The focus then shifts away from the arbitrary nature of the sign to the sign's motivation. What are the causes that explain that a given word is the way it is? For what non-random reasons have such a signifier and such a signified been associated? This type of research constitutes the motivational approach¹. On this basis,

¹ For a general presentation of motivation, its applications, its usefulness in etymological research, etc., see Del Giudice (2022).

etymologically and phonetically unrelated forms can be grouped together in the same category.

This is why, in the case of dialectal names for the robin in France, *roupie* (< *roux* ‘ginger’ + *pit* ‘chest’), *pierrot* (*pit* + *roux*), *gavach roge* (literally ‘ginger throat’) and *pitre jaune* (literally ‘yellow chest’), which all refer to the fact that the bird’s plumage features a reddish medallion, need to be classified in the same motivational category. All these linguistic forms are generated by the same motive. An inventory of data larger than the handful of examples taken here would show that, for the robin, this colored medallion motive is overwhelmingly dominant throughout France. In contrast, the name *bovet* (literally ‘little ox’), inspired by the animal’s compact shape, is another type of designation that is not very widespread. In fact, the latter term is found very close to the heart of the French bullfighting tradition, where bovids are of particular cultural importance. Fig. 5 contrasts the treatment of the above five names according to a traditional map (left) and according to a motivational map (right), which highlights the originality of the second motive and the fact that it is found in a well-defined area.

Fig. 5 Traditional and motivation treatments of an identical set of data

2.2. Examples of motivational studies

While the motivational point of view can sometimes call into question the achievements of the traditional approach (e.g. does the principle of the continuity of areas have the value of an absolute law in a motivated conception of language?), in practice it is a means of extending and exploiting differently the results obtained from classical methods, often without opposing them.

For example, having collected hundreds of dialectal designations of ‘mountain’ and ‘mound’ in the Gallo-Romance area in the ALF and ALFR², Del Giudice (2020) demonstrates that, beyond their formal differences, they are generated by 6 major fundamental representations – motives – which tend to be distributed differently depending on whether populations are located at altitude or at the foot of mountains, thus resolving the etymological problem of certain forms that had remained obscure until then. To achieve this, it was necessary to carry out a cartography of motives, complementary to the cartography of linguistic forms found in classic atlases.

In another vein, Dalbera (2001; 2006: 219–220) provides an interesting case of motivational research based on formal observations and phenomena familiar to the traditional approach. Based on the recurring motives that he identifies in the Romance-speaking world, Dalbera explains why the slow worm (*anguis fragilis*) may bear names derived from the Arabic *al-‘aqrab*, originally meaning ‘scorpion’. In the Romance world, it is common for the slow worm to bear the name of the snake, but very unexpected that it should borrow that of the scorpion. The source of this name was therefore to be found elsewhere, and it all began with outcomes of lat. CURTIONE ‘snake’ of the *escurzón* type which, undergoing a paronymic attraction from *escorpión* ‘scorpion’, took on the form of the latter word, following a certain geographical progression, so that certain dialects (in particular in an intermediate zone between the territory where *escurzón* ‘slow worm’ is dominant and the area where *escorpión* ‘slow worm’ is) present mixed forms, *escurzión* being the best example. The massive presence of words evolved from *al-‘aqrab* in areas in contact with *escorpión*, would then only be the result of a particular case of synonymic substitution³, from the Romance word to the word of Arabic origin meaning ‘scorpion’. Fig. 6 shows a schematic representation of this change mechanism, based on ALEANR data and the “Orvet – 1” map of the *Atlas Linguistique Roman* (ALiR). Together with the *Atlas Linguarum europae* (ALE), this motivational atlas forms a reference set for large-scale motivational studies.

² *Atlas Linguistiques et ethnographiques de la France par Régions*, produced from the 1960s onwards. These are classic geolinguistic tools in the ALF tradition. The ALP, mentioned above, is part of this collection.

³ See Iwata (2021).

Fig. 6 Iberian names for 'slow worm', from *escurzón* to the words developed from *al-ʿaqrab*

3. Comparing Japanese dialects and the Romance world

3.1. A unique scale of analysis for dialect data

The studies cited so far might suggest that motivational analysis is confined to explaining phenomena at a more or less local level. However, one of the strengths of this approach dedicated to representations is that it touches on both cultural and cognitive aspects, and thus enables us to observe the potency of certain designation reflexes across borders and continents.

To assess this, we compared Japanese and Romance dialectal items. In other words, we brought together cultures and territories that are extremely far apart. We selected 2 examples ('praying mantis' and 'tadpole') from the onomasiological maps common to the *Linguistic Atlas of Japan* (LAJ) and the ALiR. Everything that follows will show that analyses of such geographical scope and depth in terms of the functioning of the naming act would have been difficult without taking motivational aspects into account. The examples given below therefore draw the reader's attention to the similarities

between Japanese and Romance naming. But one should not lose sight of the fact that there are also important differences between these two dialectal areas.

3.2. The praying mantis

Table 1 shows – purely by way of illustration – a very small sample of dialectal forms meaning ‘praying mantis’, among all those found in Romance languages and on the Japanese archipelago.

Table 1 A few dialectal forms meaning ‘praying mantis’

Romance forms (ALiR 2.a)	Japanese forms (LAJ maps 229, 230)
pr,ɛɡad'iw	ogamimusi
rɾ'ɛzɐ rɾ'ɛzɐ	ogamu
mɛr'ie l'ovɐ	ogametaroo
k'orta	itokirimusi
sɛyam'anu	kusakarimusi
serram'anos	nokogirimusi
kav'alfo	syorouma
k'adɖu e d'eʊs	hotokeuma
kɛvɛl'ipu di n'ɔsɛ sip'ore	dondomusi

The first observation to be made from this initial comparison is that a dialectology that focuses all its attention on forms is completely at a loss when it comes to comparing languages that have no genetic relationship with each other. In its original state, the LAJ map legend is perfectly inapplicable to a map representing the Romance territory. On this basis, the only comment that can be made is: “the forms meaning ‘praying mantis’ in Japan and the Romance-speaking area have nothing to do with each other”. The impossibility of going any further makes the comparison meaningless.

But this all changes with motivational analysis. It is now a matter of questioning the fundamental representations (i.e. motives) that gave rise to the various names for the mantis. To access these representations, we need to look at how they were “translated” into words during the lexical creation process, since these expressions always have their own literal meaning, which can be called *désignant*, and which, when naming an object in reality, makes it possible to associate linguistic material with a referent in an easily intelligible way. In what follows, *désignants* are presented between curved angle brackets (<>).

Table 2 repeats the forms in Table 1, adding the *désignants*. Thus pr,ɛɡad'iw ‘praying mantis’ breaks down into *prɛɡa* ‘pray’ + *Dieu* ‘God’ and we understand that what motivates this name is the shape and position of the insect that seems to join its limbs to pray. This motive appears in the right-hand column of the table, grouping together a set of *désignants* inspired by the same guiding representation. The whole table functions according to this principle.

Table 2 Same forms as in Table 1, with *désignants* and motives

Romance (ALiR 2.a ⁴)		Japanese (LAJ maps 229, 230)		Motives
Forms	<i>Désignants</i>	Forms	<i>Désignants</i>	
pr'ɛgɑd'iw	<God-praying (insect)>	ogamimusi	<praying insect>	1. The posture of the mantis that looks like it is praying
rr'ɛzɛ rr'ɛzɛ	<pray pray>	ogamu	<pray>	
mɛr'ie l'ovɛ	<Mary-praying (insect)>	ogametaroo	<praying Jack>	
k'orta	<cut!>	itokirimusi	<thread-cutting insect>	2. The mantis's limbs resembling cutting tools
sɛyam'anu	<hand-cutting (insect)>	kusakarimusi	<grass-cutting insect>	
serram'anos	<hand-sawing (insect)>	nokogirimusi	<saw-insect>	
kav'allo	<horse>	syorouma	<horse (of the soul of the departed?)>	3. A general comparison with the horse, sometimes with a religious reference
k'ɑdʒu e d'eʊs	<horse of God>	hotokeuma	<horse of Buddha>	
kɛvɛl'ɪnu di n'osɛ sip'orɛ	<horse of Saint Mary>	dondomusi	<horse insect>	

It is striking that dialectal terms that have absolutely nothing in common in terms of form, reveal representations and naming procedures that are so common from the Mediterranean basin to Japan. This method seems to reveal, thanks to dialectal data, certain mechanisms of human cognition, which etymologists are increasingly trying to take advantage of.

To convince ourselves that these are not isolated facts due to mere chance, we can project onto a map the very numerous data relating to the three motives presented above⁵. In the classification of Japanese data for this section and the following one, we used exclusively the resources of the *Linguistic Atlas of Japan Database* (LAJDB)⁶ that were a decisive help. The map that we propose here (Fig. 7) was produced using ShinyDialect⁷, an online cartographic tool capable of automatically producing areal maps extrapolated from point data, but which does not yet allow the display of multiple responses for the same survey point. When several motives were attested in the same Japanese locality, we chose to systematically favor the least common motive on a national scale. We sometimes tried to apply the same principle to single responses that seemed to condense two different motives.

Some forms were difficult to classify. We chose to classify *ogama*-type forms in the prayer motive, bearing in mind that they may not be unrelated to *kama* ‘sickle’. On the

⁴ See all the data in García Mouton (2001).

⁵ For reasons of size and balance, we have decided not to include Romania on our maps. This does not mean, however, that this language area is at odds with our observations. The patterns described in this article are also found in Romania.

⁶ <https://www.lajdb.org/>. More information about the LAJDB is to be found in Kumagai (2016).

⁷ <https://ljk-codes.imag.fr/shinydialect-v2/>.

other hand, it seemed natural to classify compound forms containing *kama* as ‘bladelike limbs’, even when the other part of the word was not clearly identified. To limit the risk of error, we avoided classifying some uncertain data, unless the LAJ comments invited us to do so. For example, *-kiri*, on its own and as a possible avatar of *kirigirisu* ‘kind of grasshopper’ (LAJ comments, vol. 5, p. 91), did not justify inclusion in the ‘bladelike limbs’ category, even though there should be no shortage of speakers who see it as a form related to *kiru* ‘to cut’. We have therefore decided not to classify forms such as *ibokiri(musi)* or *kubokiri*.

For the rest, we think we have followed common sense. In the motivational category of prayer we have included both explicit designations of prayer and forms such as *negisama* ⟨shinto priest⟩, which are not unlike Romance names for the mantis (one thinks of *monaca* ⟨nun⟩ or *cura* ⟨priest⟩).

The “other” category brings together all the other forms: those that represent other motives, and those we couldn’t classify with any certainty.

Fig. 7 Principal motives for 'praying mantis'

Despite the limited amount of data available for Spain, Italy and, above all, France, it is very clear that commonalities between the Romance world and Japan can be observed in various parts of the two large areas under consideration. Sardinia and a locality in Galicia thus echo standard Japanese, while western Japan responds to Portugal and the Catalan-Occitan area (plus a few Italian localities) for the image of the praying insect. The image of the horse, dominant in Corsica and scattered throughout the rest of the Romance area, is present very sporadically, but throughout the entire length of Western Japan.

The commonalities between Japan and the Romance domain are therefore undeniable. And yet, within these common motives, an element of cultural specificity emerges, as the {horse of God} (or of the Virgin, or of a Saint) becomes notably {horse of Buddha} in Tokushima Prefecture and on the island of Awaji⁸.

Other phenomena common to both linguistic groups have not been included in this article. One thinks in particular of the many names shared between mantis, grasshopper, cricket or other more unexpected species ({snake} in Italo-Romantic, {lizard} in Japanese).

Finally, some Japanese motives seem absent in the West, such as that manifested by the name *ibomushi* {wart insect}, based on the archipelago's popular belief that warts disappear if they are presented to mantises to gnaw on. Conversely, there are romance motives not observed in Japan.

3.3. The tadpole

In a similar vein, Del Giudice (2022) draws an equivalent parallel between Japanese dialects and the languages spoken in the vicinity of the city of Nice, regarding tadpole designations. As with the praying mantis, the motives common to Japan and this tiny Romance area are obvious. Some of these data are recalled as a sample in Table 3 (where Occitan forms from other regions have been added as a complement, indicated in italics).

⁸ The fact that the mantis is called {horse} may simply be due to the fact that this insect is perceived as a kind of grasshopper, itself sometimes called a horse – at least in Western languages. The explanation given by the ALE commentary (1.1., p. 147), according to which the horse is a jumping animal in the same way as the grasshopper, would deserve to be put in competition with other leads.

Table 3 ‘tadpole’: dialectal forms, *désignants* and motives

Occitan (THESOC, ALF...)		Japanese (LAJ maps 221, 222, 223)		Motives
Forms	<i>Désignants</i>	Forms	<i>Désignants</i>	
babiòt	{toad (+ diminutive suffix)}	kaerunoko	{frog baby}	1. The tadpole is just seen as a frog, a toad (often as a baby frog, a baby toad)
babion	{toad (+ diminutive suffix)}	hikinoko	{toad baby}	
<i>granhotil</i>	{frog (+ diminutive suffix)}	wakudonko	{frog baby}	
testassa	{head (+ augmentative suffix)}	atamadekka	{head (+ big?)}	2. The tadpole has a remarkably big head
testard	{head (+ suffix)}	atamabuto	{head (+ thick?)}	
<i>capgròs</i>	{big head}	atamadaezin	{head (+ ?)}	
caceta	{ladle (+ diminutive suffix)}	otamazyakusi	{ladle}	3. The shape of the tadpole is reminiscent of kitchen utensils
paeleta	{frying pan (+ diminutive suffix)}	syamozi	{rice scoop}	
<i>culhièra</i>	{spoon}	nabehuta	{pot lid}	

Once again, the three main motives of the Nice region, well shared by Japanese dialects, appear in the right-hand column of the table. In addition to the Occitan-speaking regions, they are also abundantly represented throughout the Romance world.

Extending the study area to a wider Romance scale⁹, then projecting onto a map all the ALiR¹⁰ and LAJDB data corresponding to one of these three motives¹¹, we obtain Fig. 8.

As in Fig. 7, we had to eliminate multiple responses and find a solution for hybrid forms. To this end, we gave priority to non-standard forms. We also favored the representation of the “head” motive, which is quite rare in the Japanese archipelago (it is represented on the map by round dots that make it stand out more clearly). This is why an interesting case such as *atamazyakusi* (where *atama* ‘head’ appears) has been

⁹ And even beyond, since we have added non-Romance data from Brittany and the Basque Country (for the latter, the data is even non-Indo-European). To map these two areas, we have used the *Nouvel Atlas Linguistique de la Basse-Bretagne* (NALBB, map 235) and the *Euskararen Herri Hizkeren Atlas* (EHHA, map 118).

¹⁰ Completed – and where necessary slightly revised – using information from the *Atlas Linguistique et ethnographique de la Picardie* (ALPic, map 601), the *Atlas Linguistique et ethnographique de la Champagne et de la Brie* (ALCB, map 1115) and Tuaille & Stiers (1986).

¹¹ As with mantis, we have taken into account the LAJ’s comments for Japanese dialectal terms that we were unable to interpret ourselves. Thus, all the forms *atamabuto*, *atamabukko*, *atamahucyage*, *atamadekka*, *atamadaezin*, *suburubuuta*, *taaciburaa* were linked to the motivation of the head, following the remark “all of these forms are thought to focus on the big head of the tadpole” (「いずれも『おたまじゃくし』の頭の大きいことに注目した語形と考えられる」) (vol. 5, p. 67).

placed in the “head” category and not in “kitchen utensil”, even though the proximity of this form to *otamazyakusi* is obvious.

Alongside the three motives shown in Table 3, we wanted to highlight the distribution of a particular lexical type. This is *otama* when not followed by *-zyakusi*. This type includes forms generally in geographical contact with *otamazyakusi*, such as *otama* and its avatars *otamakko*, *otamacryo(o)*, *kaerottama*, etc. The LAJ comments themselves hesitate to see *otama* as a simple truncation of *otamazyakusi* or as a base *tama* ‘ball’ (p. 66), itself possibly induced by *atama* ‘head’ (p. 67). On the other hand, our map incorporates into the pattern “frog, toad (baby frog, baby toad)” Romance designations such as {frog egg, toad egg}, which the Japanese form *otamago* also seems to vaguely echo (*tamago* meaning ‘egg’). Forms with *otama* are therefore likely to condense several motives. We have preferred to project the *otama* type itself without deciding on its fascinating ambiguity.

In other cases where we had doubts, prudence led us to abstain, which deprives some data of a projection on the map. For example, in *gorokko* we thought we recognized *gaerokko* (= *gaeruko* {baby frog}). We were also tempted to see in *genguruko*, *ge(e)kuro* distorted forms – clearly metathetical for the second – of *gaeru(no)ko*. But in all these cases, the comments (pp. 68–69) seemed to interpret things differently or remained rather unexplicit, ultimately convincing us not to map the forms concerned. In this case, the loss is not noticeable, as the “frog, toad” motive is already abundantly represented on the map of Japan. It could even have been more abundant, but we didn’t keep forms where the modifier meant ‘frog’, whenever the identity of the modified word was unclear. This was the case, for example, with *gaerukuta* and *gaeruma(n)cyo*. All this being said, the presence of gaps and probable errors in our map concerns only a very small part of the data.

Fig. 8 Principal motives for 'tadpole'

The main impression to be gained from Fig. 8 is that, as expected, motives are common to both Western Europe and Japan, but in very contrasting proportions. The idea of the head, particularly prevalent in France and Sardinia, carries infinitely less weight in Japan, where the corresponding forms are marginal. Paradoxically, the strength of this representation is indisputable, for in this country where *otamazyakusi* and the frog motive reign supreme, it can be found, in a fragmented way and in very different forms, from the far south (Ryukyu Islands) to Iwate Prefecture in northern Honshu. Are these ancient forms in retreat because of the dominant types, or more recent creations/reconstructions, possibly accidental, driven by the obvious anatomical specificity of the tadpole?

The other main motives are fairly evenly distributed between the two main areas studied, although it is worth noting that the comparison between tadpoles and kitchen utensils relies almost exclusively, in Japan, on the *otamazyakusi* type, whose generous distribution may well have been favored by the weight of the standard. Nonetheless, this map allows us to verify once again that Japan and the Romance world do indeed use common representations to name similar referents.

To keep it as simple and evocative as possible, Fig. 8 (like Fig. 7) is limited to 3 outstanding motives, although others could have been mentioned. The motivational classification proposed by Médélice (2009) is much more complete and precise than the overview given here. In particular, she mentions the names of various tools (hammer, fork, nail...) and comparisons with fish, which are not considered in our map¹². Readers interested in finding out more are invited to take a look at ALIR's comments.

4. Beyond praying mantises and tadpoles

4.1. Complementary data: “easy motives” and more surprising representations

The designations of the praying mantis and the tadpole, in Japanese and Romance dialects, were good examples for outlining a number of naming reflexes widely shared across these two territories. Apart from ‘mantis’ and ‘tadpole’, not all concepts allow us to draw such massive parallels from one linguistic space to another, but cross-border motives are nonetheless observed with fairly significant regularity. We might point out that a scarecrow is literally the object that frightens crows, and that the same *désignant* is found in the Japanese word *karasuodosu* (*karasu* ‘crow’ + *odosu* ‘scare’, LAJ map 190), alongside other similar names such as *suzumeodosi* (*suzume* ‘sparrow’ + *odosi* ‘what scares’), which is reminiscent of the Nicoise *espavèntapàsseras* (*espavènta*

¹² A number of forms such as *otamazyakko*, *otamadozyoo*, *otamakkozyoro*, whose head refers to the notion of fish, are classified in our map as “*otama* type”.

‘scares’ + *pàsseras* ‘sparrows’). Sometimes the idea of scaring is enough in itself, and *odosi*, *odosu* is rendered in Occitan as *espaventat*, *espaurugat* (derivatives of *espaventar*, *espaurugar* ‘scare’). Another name, *waraninyoo* (‘straw’ + ‘puppet’), is not discordant with the form *palhasso* (traditional carnival puppet made of straw) used in the region of Nice to designate the scarecrow.

These fundamental denominations often seem to be generated by fairly obvious representations (the tadpole is a frog, the scarecrow is a man of straw), whether original forms or forms that were subsequently remotivated (in this respect, the tadpole offers several examples of remotivation-condensations such as *atamajyakusi* and *otama*). But sometimes, shared representations are a little more surprising. It is the case for the mantis, when it is seen as a holy horse, or for the owl (LAJ, map 212) when it is compared with a cat. And once again, forms like *nekodori* {cat-bird} or *mya(a)cuko* {meow + ?} look particularly similar to occitan *catamiaula* (‘female cat’ + ‘to mew 3sg’), *miaula*, *miauneta* {mew (+ diminutive suffix)} or french *chat-huant* {hooting cat}. It is also a safe bet that *yo-* in a number of Japanese designations (*yotori*, *yotaka*, *yohukuro*, *yocuku*...) means ‘night’, just as this bird is called *nuechola* {night (+ diminutive suffix)} in several Occitan dialects. It is on correspondences of this kind that research is now trying to break through the most obscure etymologies.

4.2. Further perspectives

In any case, the common motives evoked in this article speak volumes about the way human beings interpret the world, and about the fundamental workings of language (what is it about a referent that strikes the imagination, and how do we translate this representation into words?). New words are not invented by chance, and the changes they undergo over time are often – probably more than is generally believed – linked to deep-seated representations. We therefore believe that semantic motivation is a possible gateway to more in-depth studies involving cognitivists. The aim would then be to move on from the lexical case study stage to that of the general functioning of our brain and the interface between thought and expression. A fine program for data derived from dialectology!

From a strictly geolinguistic point of view, the main purpose of Figs. 7 and 8 was to show that the phenomena mentioned are significant, since they cover considerable areas within the dialectal spaces considered and given that even the non-dominant motives (“horse” and “head”, in Japan) extend in dotted lines over hundreds of kilometers. The precise distribution of motives, however, was not decisive for our purpose. It would still be interesting to see whether words whose motive depends on the place of residence (along the lines of what was attempted in Del Giudice (2020)), give rise to similar distributions in Japan and other parts of the world. The identification of

comparable motivational areas based on geographical or social criteria (types of community) could lead to new discoveries about certain constants in the act of naming things.

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